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This deliverable provides connectors and transformers for integrating legacy systems into WILSON Personalised (Building) Data Hubs (PDHs), along with documentation on their use, metadata, and supporting microservices.	

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Full Form
BAS	Building Automation System
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BOT	Building Topology Ontology
BMS	Building Management System
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
CDE	Common Data Environment
DB	Database
EMS	Energy Management System
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
FM	Facility Management
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
IDS	International Data Space
IoT	Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
LBD	Linked Building Data
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
ODBC	Open Database Connectivity
OAS	OpenAPI Specification
OCR	Optical Character Recognition
OPC UA	Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture
PDH	Personalised Data Hub
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point

Acronym	Full Form
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
RAM	Reference Architecture Model
REST	Representational State Transfer
RML	RDF Mapping Language
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RVT	Revit Project File Format (Autodesk)
SDK	Software Development Kit
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
SOSA	Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator (ontology)
SSN	Semantic Sensor Network (ontology)
SQL	Structured Query Language
UI	User Interface
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 7.3 “Connectors to legacy and third party systems” presents the architecture and implementation framework for connectors that enable seamless interoperability between the WILSON ecosystem and diverse data sources, ranging from legacy systems to modern third-party applications. At the core of this approach is the *Personalised (Building) Data Hub (PDH)*, which acts as a decentralised integration layer standardising the access to heterogeneous systems through purpose-built connectors (hereafter referred to as **PDH connectors**).

The building sector is characterised by fragmented digital ecosystems, where legacy tools, proprietary systems, and modern (cloud) platforms coexist but rarely interoperate. This lack of connectivity limits the reuse of data across the building lifecycle.

Two types of connectors have been developed. **Legacy connectors** extract data from non-API sources (e.g., IFC and Revit files, Excel spreadsheets, isolated databases) and convert it into structured, semantically rich formats using Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) processes. These enable, for example, converting Building Information Modelling (BIM) data to Linked Building Data (LBD) using established ontologies such as Brick and Building Topology Ontology (BOT), as well as enabling queriable knowledge graphs for digital logbooks and lifecycle assessments. **Third-party connectors**, on the other hand, leverage Representational State Transfer (RESTful) Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) and Software Development Kits (SDKs) to integrate with modern (cloud) platforms and external services (e.g., weather APIs), enabling real-time, bidirectional data exchange for predictive analytics, energy optimisation, and external tool integration.

By enabling seamless data exchange, the PDH connectors bring value to a wide range of stakeholders, i.e., facility managers gain meaningful insights into building operation, technology providers benefit from easier system integration, policymakers can rely on harmonised data streams to support EU objectives, and end users benefit from more efficient, sustainable, and resilient buildings.

All connectors are designed within a modular, secure, and future-proof architecture aligned with the WILSON Data Space framework, which ensures semantic interoperability, data sovereignty, and adherence to access control policies. They adopt OpenAPI-based standardised interfaces, Resource Description Framework (RDF)/ JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data (JSON-LD) for semantic modelling, and an interface with the WILSON Data Space vocabulary hub for consistent metadata annotation. Security and trust are ensured through OAuth2/API key authentication and rigorous compatibility testing, ensuring secure and robust operation across the PDH and the wider WILSON infrastructure. This approach is fully aligned with the European Data Spaces Vision, ensuring data sovereignty, interoperability and trust, while supporting the digital transformation of the built environment.

This structured approach delivers scalable, standards-based connectivity across building management systems, allowing for both primary operations and advanced secondary data usage. Beyond WILSON, this implementation framework provides a scalable foundation for

adoption across other European initiatives, fostering long-term innovation in data-driven building management and lifecycle sustainability.

2. INTRODUCTION

Interoperability and efficient data exchange remain among the major barriers to digital transformation in the built environment. Building Information Models (BIM), Building Management Systems (BMS), legacy applications, and external services often operate in silos, using incompatible formats, protocols, and data models. This fragmentation limits data reuse across the building lifecycle and hinders sustainability and efficiency in building operation.

The WILSON project addresses these challenges by creating a robust interoperability framework that allows legacy and third-party systems to interact seamlessly with the WILSON Data Space and Personalised Data Hubs (PDHs). The primary technical outcome is a modular set of connectors that enable standardised data exchange between diverse platforms such as BIM, BMS, and legacy applications. In other words, within this framework, PDH connectors are the key enablers of standardised data exchange, acting as modular translation components between heterogeneous data sources and platforms. These connectors implement Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) pipelines that comply to the semantic and technical standards defined by the WILSON DS initiative, ensuring that data is handled consistently across all systems. They support both legacy integrations, such as converting IFC or Revit files, Excel spreadsheets, and isolated databases into semantically rich, machine-readable formats, and third-party integration through Representational State Transfer (RESTful) Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) and Software Development Kits (SDKs) with cloud-based services and external data providers.

Additionally, this *Deliverable* introduces the initial implementation of PDH connectors and their supporting metadata structures that enable traceability and harmonisation of ingested data. These components ensure that data ingestion and transformation processes comply with the semantic and technical standards defined by the WILSON Data Space initiative (*Deliverable 5.1*). In doing so, the developed PDH connectors provide traceability, harmonisation, and security across heterogeneous data sources. Along with the software components, the *Deliverable* includes detailed documentation and integration guidelines to support deployment, testing and validation in pilot environments.

The outcomes presented in this document lay the foundation for reliable, secure, standards-based connectivity across building data ecosystems. These findings lay the groundwork for reliable data ingestion and transformation within the WILSON architecture. Beyond the technical performance within WILSON pilots, the results and their corresponding implementation also contribute to broader EU objectives on interoperability, data sovereignty, sustainability and digitalisation of the built environment.

The remainder of this section is organised as follows. Section 2.1 defines the scope of the *Deliverable*, outlining its objectives and boundaries. Section 2.2 describes the structure of the document, while Section 2.3 discusses the relation to other tasks and deliverables within WILSON.

2.1. Scope of the *Deliverable*

This *Deliverable* provides the first version of the WILSON project report on the development of connectors and transformers for legacy and third-party systems. It focuses on the design and implementation of PDH connectors that enable secure, standardised data exchange between traditional systems (e.g., BIM tools, BMS, local databases, and other legacy platforms or third-party systems) and the PDHs developed under *Task 7.1*.

These PDH connectors are key enablers of data interoperability between heterogeneous systems within the WILSON architecture. They implement ETL processes aligned with the semantic and technical standards of the WILSON Data Space, ensuring that heterogeneous building data can be ingested, transformed and reused consistently across applications and pilot sites, both within WILSON and beyond. Alongside the software modules, this *Deliverable* also introduces the metadata structures and integration guidelines documentation needed for achieving the targeted traceability, harmonisation and secure deployment. This is an intermediate version of *Deliverable 7.3* establishing the technical foundations for the WILSON pilots and early integration activities. The final version of this *Deliverable*, scheduled for M30 (October 31, 2026), will refine and expand the PDH connectors based on feedback from pilot deployments, also considering additional platforms. Together, these subsequent iterations will ensure the PDH connectors are robust, scalable, and fit for real-world implementation across the WILSON ecosystem and beyond.

2.2. Structure of the *Deliverable*

This *Deliverable* is organised as follows:

- **Section 1** provides the executive summary, highlighting the objectives, methodology and main results.
- **Section 2** presents the background and objectives of the PDH connectors within the WILSON interoperability strategy.
- **Section 3** outlines the technical architecture and design patterns used for developing the connectors, including their alignment with the WILSON Data Space architecture, the use of open standards (e.g., OPC-UA, RESTful APIs), and modular integration principles.
- **Section 4** presents the connector design and implementation principles for legacy and third-party applications.
- **Section 5** summarises the main outcomes.
- **Section 6** lists the cited references and supporting documentation of this *Deliverable*.

2.3. Relation with Other Tasks and Deliverables

Deliverable D7.3 is closely connected with several other components of the WILSON project:

- **WP5-6:** The semantic models and ontologies developed in *Task 5.2* provide the target schema for transforming data from legacy systems.
- **WP7-8:** This deliverable feeds directly into the PDHs developed in *Task 7.1/Task 8.1*, serving as the interface layer for heterogeneous data ingestion, and is finalized in *Task 8.3 (Deliverable D8.3)*.

- **WP9-10:** The PDH connectors support data integration from BMS and other monitoring systems (*Task 9.1/Task 10.1*), enabling both real-time and historical data use cases.
- **WP13:** Integrating the connectors into the technical infrastructure of pilot sites is essential for achieving TRL6/7 in WP13 and will support system-wide validation.

3. SYSTEM LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS

The integration of multiple data sources within the WILSON architecture requires a thorough understanding of the existing system landscape across pilot sites. This landscape includes both a) legacy systems, such as BMS, proprietary databases and file-based storage, and b) third-party platforms, which include cloud services, open data platforms and modern end-user applications. Each of these introduces distinct technical and semantic interoperability challenges that should be addressed to enable consistent data exchange within the WILSON ecosystem.

This analysis provides the foundation for creating **PDH connectors** that enable seamless data exchange between the Personalised Data Hub (PDH), the Minimum Viable Data Space (MVDS) infrastructure, and other diverse systems and external applications, such as internal databases, enterprise applications, Building Automation Systems (BAS), and cloud-based APIs. Each of these components introduces unique technical and semantic challenges that must be addressed to ensure interoperability and consistent data flow across the entire WILSON ecosystem. By mapping current practices, identifying integration gaps and classifying systems according to their interoperability requirements, this analysis ensures that the connector development is grounded in real operational contexts.

To address the above, Section 3.1 provides an overview detailing the different types of legacy systems and the challenges associated with their integration (Section 3.1.1), as well as the identification and documentation of these systems (Section 3.1.2). Section 3.2 examines third-party systems, covering Building Management Systems (BMS) (Section 3.2.1), Building Automation Systems (BAS) (Section 3.2.2), Energy Management Systems (EMS) (Section 3.2.3), SharePoint and existing databases (Section 3.2.4), and external data sources such as weather APIs (Section 3.2.5). Section 3.3 introduces PDH connectors, explaining their role within the system architecture (Section 3.3.1) and their relationship with WILSON Data Space connectors (Section 3.3.2).

3.1. Overview of Legacy Systems: Legacy System Types and Integration Challenges

Legacy systems remain central to many building operations, but they frequently lack modern connectivity features, making integration difficult [1]. Many of them were developed decades ago, using proprietary protocols or file-based workflows that lack modern interfaces. As a result, they operate in silos, preventing cross-domain data sharing, reuse and limiting the ability to perform advanced workflows. Nevertheless, these systems are still deeply embedded in current operational workflows and understanding them is critical for designing PDH connectors that bridge existing infrastructures and the WILSON architecture.

Definition: Legacy System

A **legacy system** is an existing software or hardware platform that uses outdated technologies, architectures, or interfaces. These systems often lack standardised integration mechanisms, such as modern APIs or semantic models. Examples include legacy databases, custom software, and proprietary control systems.

Several categories of legacy systems have been identified within WILSON:

- *In-house Relational Databases (e.g., PostgreSQL)*: Store structured operational and maintenance records, but often isolated and lacking semantic schemas. They are typically required for both historical reference and real-time facility management information.
- *Local File Storage Repositories*: Contain image archives, PDFs, CAD/IFC models, point clouds, etc., essential for asset management and digital twin modelling but difficult to query or integrate.
- *Custom Monitoring Tools*: Custom dashboards or scripts for energy monitoring, fault detection, and diagnostics, usually without standardised APIs or external data-sharing capabilities.
- *Legacy BMS/BAS Controllers*: Older BMS and BAS devices that use proprietary or legacy protocols (e.g., Modbus, BACnet MS/TP) and lack modern RESTful interfaces or semantic interoperability.

These systems represent valuable data sources but often function in silos, which limits cross-domain data sharing and advanced analytics [2]. They also represent key integration challenges such as lack of standard interfaces, inconsistent semantics, and fragmented access control. Despite these limitations, they continue to be used as they are deeply embedded in existing workflows and are costly to replace. Table 1 shows the current state of legacy and operational systems that support each data category across WILSON pilots, as described in *Section 4.5 of Deliverable D4.4*. It highlights both capabilities and gaps (e.g., the limited sharing of environmental data in most pilots). Within WILSON, PDH connectors are designed to address these issues by translating legacy formats into interoperable, semantically enriched data, ensuring that it can be reused across applications without replacing existing infrastructure. The PDHs will connect to these legacy systems through standardised WILSON Data Space connectors, APIs, and ETL pipelines, without replacing them.

Table 1. List of Legacy Systems at different Pilots in WILSON

Data Categories		Pilot			
		Italy	Spain	UK	Switzerland
	Sensor data	BMS & district meters	Hospital BMS sensors	ABB BMS (Spark), Siemens Desigo (Core), USB BMS	Smart meters (heat, water, EV)
	Building systems data	Central building BMS (HVAC, fire safety)	Hospital BMS	Spark: ABB BMS, Core: Siemens Desigo, USB: BMS API	Heat pump & EV charger meters
	Energy management data	District heating/cooling + PV	Hospital BMS	BMS meters, PV API (USB)	PV, EV charger, smart meters
	User specific data	Not present	Not present	Occupancy sensors (USB), survey forms (Spark, Core)	Household-level consumption logs
	Maintenance & operations data	CAFM system	CAFM, hospital IT O&M	Spark: Track Record & Concerto; Core: E-Logbooks	SAP tool
	Point cloud model data	Photogrammetry scans	Licensed scans stored locally	Revit/IFC models (local repositories)	Not available
	BIM data	IFC/Revit	Hospital IFC/Revit	Revit/IFC models stored locally	Not available
	External data	None	None	None	None
	Environmental data	None	None	None	None
	Financial/economic data	Limited	Regulatory reporting docs	None	None

3.1.1. Identification and Documentation of Legacy Systems

To facilitate effective integration, a structured and systematic process for identifying and documenting legacy systems has been applied across all WILSON pilot sites. This step is essential, as the precise understanding of existing infrastructures provides the basis for implementing PDH connectors that can reliably extract, transform, and harmonise data from heterogeneous sources. It entails mapping the entire data lifecycle, from generation at the physical layer (i.e., IoT devices, sensors) to processing, and storage in local systems. The methodology combines the following main activities:

- *Inventory Creation*: Compiling a comprehensive list of legacy systems at each pilot site, including vendor information, version, communication protocols, and supported data formats.
- *Interface Assessment*: Assessment of each system's connectivity options, including RESTful APIs, OPC UA, MQTT, or file-based exports to determine integration feasibility.
- *Data Schema Mapping*: Extracting and analysing logical models from relational databases and semi-structured formats to capture the underlying semantics of stored data and identify gaps.
- *Access Control Review*: Document authentication methods, authorisation and access control policies to ensure secure and compliant data extraction.

This process results in site-specific integration blueprints for each pilot, these blueprints capture the technical capabilities and limitations of existing systems and directly inform the design of PDH-based connectors. Special attention is given to systems requiring middleware or protocol conversion tools to translate legacy communication standards into the RESTful API-driven PDH interface.

3.2. Overview of Third-Party Systems

While legacy platforms dominate many building operations, third-party systems are platforms and services that are developed by another organisation and can be used for either primary or secondary data [3]. Such systems are increasingly used to provide complementary services and modern functionality. They include commercial software, enterprise platforms, and open-source tools. The WILSON framework classifies these systems based on their functional domain and the level of integration required.

Definition: Third-Party System

A **third-party system** is an external proprietary or managed open-source application developed outside the organisation that uses modern integration practices and typically exposes data through APIs, SDKs, or other standardised interfaces.

Table 2 lists the third-party platforms, services, APIs, and external systems used by each pilot to collect, store, or process data. These include cloud platforms (e.g., smart-me Cloud), open data portals (e.g., Urban Observatory), BIM tools (e.g., Revit, IFC), weather databases, energy grid interfaces, and collaborative platforms such as SharePoint, as described in Section 4.5 of *Deliverable D4.4*. Integration with these systems is achieved through APIs, WILSON DS connectors, or secure gateways. Notable examples include the Urban Observatory (UK) and smart-me Cloud (IT), which provide real-time data access. SharePoint (CH) is used as a controlled collaboration platform for BIM models and point cloud sharing.

Although these systems generally provide modern integration options, they still introduce significant interoperability challenges such as:

- API heterogeneity: different formats (e.g., RESTful, GraphQL), potentially inconsistent data models and varying documentation quality.
- Licensing and access control limitations: forced reliance on vendor-specific authentication methods (i.e., API keys) and data use limitations.
- Semantic inconsistency and misalignment: lack of consistent ontologies or vocabularies across providers.

Sections 3.2.1 – 3.2.5 detail the key third-party systems identified within the WILSON ecosystem.

Table 2. List of Third-Party Systems at different Pilots in WILSON

Data Categories		Pilot			
		Italy	Spain	UK	Switzerland
	Sensor data	None (all local)	VPN-secured access, no third-party	Demand Logic (Spark), Urban Observatory API (USB)	smart-me Cloud
	Building systems data	None	VPN-secured hospital IT system	Demand Logic acquisition device (Spark); VPN remote access (Core)	smart-me Cloud
	Energy management data	None	None	Bring Energy dashboards (Spark); Open Energy Dashboard (Core); HELIX Open Data Portal (USB)	smart-me Cloud (PV, tariffs, storage)
	User specific data	None	None	Urban Observatory (USB), anonymized survey repository (Core)	smart-me Cloud (household data, restricted)
	Maintenance & operations data	None	None	Track Record (Spark), Concerto (Spark), e-Logbooks (Core), HELIX Open Portal (USB aggregated O&M)	SAP tool
	Point cloud model data	Licensed photogrammetry contractor	Licensed BIM vendor	Revit/IFC shared under CC-BY-NC via third-party repository (Zenodo/Urban Observatory)	Not available
	BIM data	IFC/Revit through contractors	Licensed IFC/Revit	Zenodo & Urban Observatory (USB), CC-BY-NC licensing	Not available
	External data	None	Weather APIs, compliance databases	HELIX Open Data Portal; Urban Observatory (USB)	Not available
	Environmental data	None	None	Urban Observatory API (air quality, occupancy, environment)	Not available

Data Categories		Pilot			
		Italy	Spain	UK	Switzerland
	Financial/economic data	None	None	Open Energy Dashboard (Core)	Not available

3.2.1. Building Management Systems (BMS)

BMS platforms are a cornerstone of building operation that enable centralised monitoring and control of mechanical and electrical equipment, including Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC), lighting, security, and fire safety systems [4]. Examples include Siemens Desigo, Johnson Controls Metasys, and Schneider Electric EcoStruxure. BMS platforms are among the most data-rich sources, offering continuous streams of information that are essential for improving the operational efficiency of buildings. Although many BMS platforms have APIs, they frequently require specialised drivers for data retrieval. Proprietary protocols and vendor lock-in (e.g., BACnet, KNX) often limit interoperability. Data heterogeneity further leads to inconsistencies in time-series formatting, naming conventions, and metadata definitions.

WILSON addresses the above challenges by developing dedicated PDH connector modules that translate BMS-specific protocols (e.g., BACnet, KNX) into RESTful endpoints accessible through the PDH, allowing integration into the WILSON architecture. Beyond the project, this approach contributes to European Data Space goals, showing how traditionally closed building platforms can be opened up to enable trusted data ecosystems.

3.2.2. Building Automation Systems (BAS)

BAS platforms focus on automated control functions and can be used as standalone solutions or as subsystems within larger BMS frameworks [5]. They typically use programmable logic controllers (PLCs) and field buses like Modbus RTU or CANopen. Within WILSON, BAS platforms represent a major source of real-time device-level data. However, BAS often exhibit hardware dependency as they rely on PLCs with limited external interfaces. Low-level protocol parsing is required for integration, as are direct hardware connections in some cases. The PDH addresses this issue by employing lightweight connector modules that poll device registers and publish normalised telemetry data for subsequent use.

3.2.3. Energy Management Systems (EMS)

EMS platforms are essential to tracking utility performance, analysing and optimising energy consumption, and facilitating sustainability reporting [6]. Examples include PowerAdvocate, SAP Energy, and Smappee. These systems frequently connect to smart meters, SCADA platforms, submetering devices, PV installations and data storage systems. As such, EMS platforms play a central role in collecting time-series data on consumption, generation, and grid interaction. This information that is vital for energy benchmarking, predictive analytics, and LCA. However, similarly to above, EMS integration also poses several challenges, e.g., different data formats and sampling rates across platforms, proprietary APIs restricting access, inconsistent semantics, etc. Integration with the PDH allows for the collection of aggregated energy data across buildings and districts, which aids in comparative analytics and carbon footprint assessments. The connector development focusses on time-series data normalisation and alignment with semantic energy vocabularies defined in the International Data Spaces (IDS) vocabulary hub.

3.2.4. SharePoint and Existing Databases

Enterprise platforms such as Microsoft SharePoint and traditional relational databases are widely used for document management and storage of administrative or operational data. Microsoft SharePoint is a popular enterprise content management platform for document storage, collaboration, and workflow automation [7]. These systems often contain essential information (e.g., maintenance logs, construction and legal documentation, technical system specifications) that complements the historical and real-time data from other systems. Despite their importance, these systems usually rely on proprietary access mechanisms, lack of consistency in semantics, and heterogeneous data structures. SharePoint instances are used in the WILSON pilots to store construction records, maintenance logs, and compliance certificates. Enterprise databases (e.g., Oracle, SQL Server) store structured information about facilities, tenants, and contracts. Connecting these systems to the PDH allows for the contextual enrichment of operational data with administrative and legal metadata. REST-based connectors facilitate data extraction and transformation, while fine-grained access control ensures adherence to governance policies. This integration transforms these static enterprise repositories into active components of the WILSON data ecosystem, enabling semantically unified access to both operational and administrative data.

3.2.5. External Data Sources (e.g., Weather APIs)

External data sources (e.g., weather APIs, solar irradiance databases) improve predictive and prescriptive analytics by providing contextual and environmental data. Weather APIs, such as OpenWeatherMap and WeatherAPI, provide real-time and forecast data, which can be combined with building energy profiles to improve demand forecasting [8]. Table 3 provides an overview of the external data sources identified in WILSON. Integration is relatively simple thanks to public REST APIs, but challenges include rate limits, authentication, and time synchronisation. The PDH addresses these issues by serving as a proxy, aggregating and caching external data to ensure consistent availability while reducing reliance on external network conditions.

Table 3. An overview of external data sources in WILSON

Data Source	API Endpoint	Data type	Use in WILSON project	Authentication
Open Data Switzerland (MeteoSwiss)	opendata.swiss/en/dataset/icon-ch1-2-eps (or via MeteoSwiss API where applicable)	Numerical weather forecast (ICON-CH1/2-EPS)	Advanced energy and HVAC optimization, scenario modelling	Public endpoint (may require registration)
OpenWeather Map	api.openweathermap.org/data/2.5/weather	Real-time weather, forecasts	Energy demand prediction, indoor comfort optimization	API Key

Data Source	API Endpoint	Data type	Use in WILSON project	Authentication
WeatherAPI	weatherapi.com/current.json	Historical and forecasted weather	HVAC scheduling optimization	API Key
OpenStreetMap Nominatim	nominatim.openstreetmap.org/search	Geolocation data	Contextual enrichment of building location	Rate-limited, no auth
Solar Irradiance API (PVGIS)	re.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pvgtools2/pvcalc.php	Solar radiation data	PV performance forecasting	Public endpoint

To address the above integration challenges, WILSON aims to develop connectors that rely on standardised interfaces based on OpenAPI and RDF/JSON-LD, apply semantic enrichment using the WILSON Data Space vocabulary hub to ensure consistent terminology and annotation across services, and implement access control to guarantee secure, reliable and compliant integration. This approach ensures that data from diverse sources and external services can be securely reused within the PDHs and WILSON Data Space, enabling advanced use cases such as energy monitoring and optimisation, data-driven asset management, predictive maintenance, renovation planning, technoeconomic investment planning, etc.

3.3. PDH Connectors

PDH is a decentralised integration layer in the WILSON architecture. It allows secure, semantically rich, and interoperable data flow between building-level systems and external stakeholders. To accomplish this, the PDH employs modular connectors that convert various data sources, such as legacy systems, third-party platforms, and IoT devices, into standardised, API-driven interfaces. These connectors are not monolithic. Each PDH connector is a custom integration module that bridges gaps in communication protocols, data structures, and access policies. They operate as translators, adapters, and security gatekeepers, ensuring that all data passing through the PDH meets technical and governance standards.

Definition: PDH connector

A **PDH connector** is a modular integration component that standardises data sharing by translating protocols, aligning semantics, and ensuring security within the PDH.

3.3.1. Role of the PDH Connectors in the WILSON Architecture

PDH connectors are located at the interface of primary data utilisation (internal operations) and secondary data usage (external services) in the overall WILSON data flow (as defined in *Deliverable D5.1* and *D7.1*). Their key roles are:

- *Data Acquisition*: Polling or subscribing to data from local systems (e.g., BMS, databases).
- *Protocol Translation*: Converting proprietary or legacy protocols (e.g., Modbus, BACnet) into REST/HTTP or MQTT.
- *Semantic Enrichment*: Raw data is annotated with metadata using shared ontologies (e.g., Brick, IDS Core).
- *Access Control Enforcement*: Prior to exposing data, use role-based and consent-driven access policies.
- *Local Caching & Aggregation*: Local storage of time series or contextual data reduces latency and external dependencies.

3.3.2. Relationship with WILSON Data Space Connectors

PDH connectors handle local data integration, whereas WILSON Data Space connectors (part of the IDS ecosystem) handle secure cross-participant data transfer. Both works together, as depicted in Figure 1:

Figure 1. Relationship of PDH Connector with WILSON DS Connectors

In this flow:

- The **PDH Connectors** collect and normalise data. They operate at the building or organisational level, focusing on the extraction, transformation, and harmonisation of data from legacy systems, third-party applications, and IoT devices. Their main objective is to standardise heterogeneous data sources into semantically enriched formats consistent with the WILSON ontologies.
- The **WILSON Data Space Connectors** send an IDS message securely to a consumer-side connector. They manage secure and governed data sharing between participants in the WILSON ecosystem and beyond. They are built upon International Data Spaces (IDS) principles and technologies, ensuring trust, traceability, and data sovereignty through mechanisms such as policy enforcement, usage control, and secure communication protocols.

Thus, the PDH functions as a pre-processing layer, preparing data for IDS-compliant sharing.

4. PDH CONNECTOR DESIGN PRINCIPLES

PDH Connectors play a critical role in the WILSON architecture, allowing heterogeneous systems to interact seamlessly with the PDH (see Figure 2). This section describes the design principles that guide the development of connectors for legacy and third-party systems, with a focus on architectural robustness, semantic interoperability, and secure integration.

Each connector follows modular microservice principles comprising i) input (that connects to legacy, third-party or external data sources), ii) transformation (executes ETL processes), iii) output (exposes normalised data to the PDH), and iv) security (for trusted interaction based on identity management). The legacy and third-party connectors are further differentiated below.

Figure 2. WILSON data flow architecture, including the PDH connector and the data cache mechanism for derived and additional data sources

Legacy connector: A legacy connector is used when the source system does not offer a modern integration method, such as an API or SDK. Instead, data is accessed through files (e.g., IFC models, Revit files, or Excel spreadsheets), databases with no exposed endpoints, or even custom applications. This raw data is extracted, parsed, and transformed by the connector before being exposed through a standardised API for downstream use. In general, legacy connectors connect older or closed systems to newer platforms.

Third-party connector: A third-party connector interfaces with systems that already have an official integration mechanism, typically through a published API or SDK. These connectors can pull or push data directly, eliminating the need to interpret raw files or perform complex operations. This improves integration reliability, maintainability, and, in many cases, brings it closer to real time.

The following sections are organised as follows. Section 4.1 focuses on connector implementation for legacy systems, including processes for converting Excel/CSV data to SQL (Section 4.1.1), IFC to Linked Building Data (LBD) conversion (Section 4.1.2), and RVT to LBD conversion (Section 4.1.3). Section 4.2 addresses connector implementation for third-party

applications, covering PDH integration with external weather APIs (Section 4.2.1) and data transfer from diverse tools to PDH (Section 4.2.2).

Note: A single tool (e.g., Excel, Revit) can fall into either category depending on whether the integration uses its files directly (legacy) or its published APIs (third-party). Table 4 list the PDH connectors for WILSON project.

Table 4. List of PDH connectors

Legacy Connectors	Third-Party Connectors
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Excel/CSV to SQL 2. IFC to LBD 3. RVT to LBD 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. PDH to WeatherAPI

4.1. Connector Implementation for Legacy Systems

Integrating legacy systems into modern data ecosystems is one of the most persistent challenges to digital transformation in the built environment. Many of these systems, which were built decades ago, were not designed with interoperability, real-time data exchange, or semantic annotation in mind. Instead, they usually expose data using non-standardized, file-based, or tightly coupled mechanisms that do not conform to modern paradigms like RESTful APIs, event-driven architectures, or knowledge graphs.

In the WILSON project, legacy systems are defined as any data source that does not have a programmable interface and must be retrieved manually or semi-automatically. Specialised connectors are created to allow them to participate in both primary and secondary data usage scenarios. As mentioned above, these PDH connectors serve the following purpose:

- Extract, interpret, and transform data from the corresponding sources
- Convert the data into formats usable by the PDH
- Ensure secure sharing within WILSON DS framework

The connector implementation involves both technical translation and semantic reconstruction, as implicit meaning in file structures or spreadsheet layouts must be explicitly expressed to support automated reasoning and cross-system analysis.

4.1.1. Excel/CSV to SQL

A common legacy integration scenario is converting flat file data (Excel or CSV) into structured relational databases [9]. Many pilot sites keep operational records, maintenance logs, and equipment inventories in Excel, which is popular for its ease of use but lacks schema enforcement, version control, and query capabilities. To integrate this data into the WILSON ecosystem, a PDH legacy connector is developed to automate the ETL process of flat files into relational databases. The connector parses source files, validates data structures, and maps attributes to the WILSON schema, converting unstructured tables into normalised SQL datasets. The detailed steps are given in ANNEX-I: Excel/CSV to SQL.

4.1.2. IFC to LBD

Another option is to convert Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) files into Linked Building Data (LBD). IFC is an open BIM data model that is inherently complex and rigid, which limits semantic interoperability and cross-domain data integration [10]. To overcome this, a PDH legacy connector converts IFC files into LBD representations, translating BIM data into machine-readable triples stored in Resource Description Framework (RDF)/ Terse RDF Triple Language (TTL) format. This enables building components to be represented as knowledge entities, with links to sensor data, maintenance records, and environmental impact databases. During this conversion process, building elements, relationships, and properties are mapped to Brick, BOT, and other WILSON - compliant ontologies. The connector performs data validation, enrichment, and metadata generation to ensure alignment with the PDH semantic model. The resulting graph, which is stored in a triple store (e.g., in .ttl file format), can be accessed using SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language (SPARQL) or REST APIs for queries such as retrieving all HVAC components in Building A that require maintenance within the next 30 days. The detailed steps are given in ANNEX-II: RVT/IFC to RDF.

4.1.3. RVT to LBD

Autodesk Revit models are widely used, but they are saved in a proprietary format (.RVT), which makes them difficult to access without using the native software. While Revit offers APIs, many workflows rely on exported IFC files, putting them in the legacy integration category [11]. The RVT-to-LBD connector uses the same semantic transformation as IFC-to-LBD, performs additional preprocessing to recover lost metadata (custom parameters, phase information, work breakdown structures), and employs heuristics to infer spatial hierarchies or classifications as needed. This makes design-time data usable in operational contexts, allowing for Digital Twin synchronisation, compliance checking, and as-built vs. as-designed comparisons.

Legacy connectors are more than just migration tools. They support incremental updates, version tracking, and change detection, as well as WILSON Data Space governance (access control, data usage provenance, and reproducibility). These mechanisms enable organisations to gradually modernise legacy systems, leveraging accumulated data within a secure, interoperable, and future-proof architecture. The detailed steps are given in ANNEX-II: RVT/IFC to RDF.

4.2. Connector Implementation for Third-Party Applications

Unlike legacy systems, third-party applications typically have standardised interfaces (e.g., REST APIs, GraphQL, SDKs). This simplifies integration, as connectors focus on orchestration, synchronisation, and policy-aware data routing rather than low-level parsing. Third-party connectors in the WILSON ecosystem provide access to external data and services, which improves building operations.

4.2.1. PDH to WeatherAPI

Weather data is a common integration requirement. The PDH-to-WeatherAPI connector retrieves real-time and forecasted meteorological data (i.e., temperature, humidity, solar

irradiance, and wind speed) and integrates it with building sensor information. Features include scheduled or event-driven data retrieval with secure authentication (API keys, OAuth2) normalisation into JSON-LD or RDF and geospatial metadata storage in the PDH time-series database for use in energy modelling, HVAC optimisation, and demand response. Local caching and fallback mechanisms will ensure availability during outages.

4.2.2. External tools and services to PDH

The developed connectors allow for bidirectional data exchange between the PDH and external services such as predictive maintenance, life cycle assessments, and energy management analytics. Functions include allowing third-party tools to query PDH data or subscribing to events that accept processed results (e.g., energy optimisation reports) back into the PDH while enforcing WILSON Data Space-compliant contracts for permitted operations, data retention, and consent. For example, a maintenance platform could analyse chiller vibration data, return diagnostic results, and integrate them into the PDH for display in the Unified Asset Management System (AMS) Graphical User Interface (GUI).

Third-party connectors must adapt to changing APIs. Key design features include abstraction layers that separate logic from API-specific configuration files for endpoints, authentication, and retry policies, as well as monitoring and alerting for failures or performance degradation. Third-party connectors follow modular and open standards, allowing new tools to be integrated quickly without disrupting existing workflows.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The work presented in this *Deliverable* marks an important step toward establishing seamless interoperability within the WILSON ecosystem. It introduces the first set of PDH connectors and the corresponding design principles that enable seamless data exchange between legacy systems, third-party applications, PDH and the broader WILSON Data Space infrastructure. Together with the defined metadata structures and integration guidelines, these connectors establish a consistent, secure, and scalable foundation for data harmonisation and reuse across pilot sites in WILSON and beyond. By delivering the initial set of PDH connectors and laying out a clear roadmap for future improvements, this *Deliverable* contributes directly to the project's broader goal of enabling efficient, standards-based data exchange across the built environment.

5.1. Main contributions

This *Deliverable* introduces the first implementation of connectors and transformers that enable interoperability between legacy and third-party systems and the PDHs. The main contributions include:

- Development of modular connectors that enable standardised data exchange between legacy platforms, modern APIs, and the PDHs,
- Implementation of ETL pipelines that comply to the WILSON DS semantic and technical standards,
- Definition of metadata structures that ensure traceability, provenance and harmonisation of ingested data.
- Provision of integration guidelines and supporting documentation to help with deployment and replication in pilot environments.

Within the WILSON architecture, these elements work together to provide consistent and reliable data ingestion across heterogeneous platforms.

5.2. Future improvements

While the current version demonstrates the feasibility of integrating various systems into the WILSON framework, further development is required to achieve full functionality and scalability. The final version of this *Deliverable* (M30, October 2026) will extend the coverage to additional platforms and data (sub)domains, improve metadata management to strengthen data governance and automation, optimise ETL and semantic enrichment processes, improve the implementation based on pilot site feedback and strengthen the alignment with existing open standards and emerging European Data Space standards, ensuring long-term reusability beyond WILSON. The latter will also ensure that the connectors are robust, scalable, and adaptable to real-world deployment scenarios beyond the built environment context.

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7. ANNEX-I: Excel/CSV to SQL

For loading Excel/CSV data into a RDBMS database, we use the open source CLI tool csvkit (current version 2.1.0)¹. The procedure to use the tool is detailed as follows:

Steps to use CSV to SQL Connector:

1. Installing the csvkit requires python. Verify if python is installed using the terminal (powershell in windows). Else download and install the latest stable version of python from the Python.org installer (prefer avoiding installation from the store in windows) and upgrade the pip to latest version.

```

1. python --version
2.
3. python -m pip install --upgrade pip
4.
5. python -m pip install csvkit
6.
7. python -m pip show csvkit
8.
9. //This should display a text as below
10.
11. Name: csvkit
12. Version: 2.1.0
13. Summary: A suite of command-line tools for working with CSV, the king of tabular file formats.
14. Home-page: https://github.com/wireservice/csvkit
15. Author: Christopher Groskopf and James McKinney
16. Author-email: chrisgroskopf@gmail.com
17. License: MIT
18.
19. Requires: agate, agate-dbf, agate-excel, agate-sql, openpyxl, sqlalchemy, xlrd
20. Required-by:
21.
    
```

2. To make the installation, globally available, we will have to update the path in environment variables (if installed using the windows store).

```

1. python -m site --user-base
2.
3. //This should print where the packages are installed in local machine or server
4.
5.
6. C:\User\Username\AppData\Local\Packages\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\LocalC
ache\local-packages
7. //look for scripts folder inside the corresponding python installation
8.
9. //Copy the path till 'Scripts' folder and add this to path in environment variables.
10.
11. //Close and reopen the terminal.
12.
13. //Test if the scripts are directly accessible using the command
14. in2csv --version
15.
16. //This should show the result
17. in2csv 2.1.0
18.
    
```

¹ <https://csvkit.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

3. Converting the excel to csv first. This conversion is recommended by the tool and also helps in enhancing performance particularly for the large files.

```

1. in2csv input.xlsx > csvOutput.csv
2.
3. //myData.csv file will be created in the same folder. We can verify the content using the
following commands.
4. head csvOutput.csv
5. or
6. Get-Content csvOutput.csv -TotalCount 5 (Windows powershell)
7.
8. //Inspect CSV content for column names
9. csvcut -n csvOutput.csv
10.
11. //if facing the encoding issues, please do the following else ignore
12. python -m pip install chardet
13. python -m chardet csvOutput.csv
14.
15. //this should give the result like this
16. csvOutput.csv: UTF-16 with confidence 1.0
17.
18. //if error still persists, try converting the excel again using the encoding.
19. in2csv input.xlsx -e "utf-16" > csvOutput.csv
20. csvcut -n csvOutput.csv --encoding "utf-16"
21.
    
```

4. It is possible to create the table structure (data model) from the csv file itself. However, it is recommended to create the tables before inserting the records from CSV.

```

1. #Approach 1 - Sniffing the first 10000 rows in csv to understand the data type
2. csvsql --tables mytable --dialect postgresql --encoding "utf-16" csvOutput.csv
3.
4. // This will generate a create table sql script. Copy and use it for creating the table.
5.
6. #Approach 2 - Create any RDBMS data base and use it for insertion
7. # create a env vars to use it later for password safety
DATABASE_URL=postgresql://user:password@localhost:5432/mydb
8.
9. # Insert (csvsql uses sqlalchemy URIs)
10. csvsql --db "$DATABASE_URL" --tables mytable --insert csvOutput.csv
11.
    
```

5. Example full flow overview of the csvkit CLI commands

```

1. # 1. convert sheet
2. in2csv --sheet "Sheet1" project_data.xlsx > project_data.csv
3.
4. # 2. quick inspect and fix header (optional)
5. csvcut -n project_data.csv
6. # rename columns or reorder if needed:
7. csvcut -c "colA,colB,colC" project_data.csv > project_data_trimmed.csv
8.
9. # 3. create table DDL for review
10. csvsql --tables project_data --snifflimit 200000 project_data_trimmed.csv > create_table.sql
11.
12. # 4. (optional) edit create_table.sql to adjust types, then run it in Postgres:
13. psql "$DATABASE_URL" -f create_table.sql
14.
15. # 5. insert
16. csvsql --db "$DATABASE_URL" --tables project_data --insert project_data_trimmed.csv
17.
    
```

6. The data from the CSV will be imported into a table in SQL database.

8. ANNEX-II: RVT/IFC to RDF

Rvt (read as Revit) and IFC are most popular output formats of BIM applications. To convert these static files into web accessible RDF (as turtles), we use a connector that can be executed locally. The output of the connector is .ttl which can be used to load on any Graph Databases. In this annexure, a procedure to use the open source IFCToLBD² converter is detailed. At this moment, there is no separate connector for RVT. Hence files are exported to IFC first to avoid any proprietary limitations of working directly with Autodesk tools.

Steps to use IFCToLBD Connector:

1. The prerequisites to run this connector is JRE. Hence JAVA installation (atleast JAVA 21) is necessary if not done earlier. Verify the version using the command in terminal.
`java -version`
2. Download the latest released java executable jar version of the connector from the github release page.

IFCToLBD v 2.44.0 Latest

Changes

- updated libraries
- example codes
- better memory handling when batch-processing files
- improved comments and documenting
- bot:interface for bounding boxes
- the desktop app is written to handle the change of user parameters at any time.
- JavaDoc for IFCToRDF
- OpenAPI updated

▼ Assets 5

Desktop2024.zip		194 MB	Oct 4, 2024
DesktopClassic.zip		194 MB	Oct 4, 2024
IFCToLBD_CLI_2_44_4.jar	sha256:e2f9bfff6d054af093...	168 MB	Aug 20
Source code (zip)			Oct 4, 2024
Source code (tar.gz)			Oct 4, 2024

3. Place the jar in the same folder as the IFC outputs.
4. Open the terminal and run the following command
`java -jar IFCToLBD_CLI_2_44_4.jar C:\User\Code\Data\spain-ll.ifc -t testoutput.ttl`
5. This will execute the conversion and a .ttl will be generated in the same folder

```
PS C:\Avinash\Code\Data> java -jar IFCToLBD_CLI_2_44_4.jar C:\Avinash\Code\Data\spain-ll.ifc -t testoutput.ttl
Target is: testoutput.ttl
C:\Users\... \AppData\Local\Temp\ifc5348446605745035446.ttl
Conversion....
Write RDF target file is: testoutput.ttl
Model print RDF
!Separate properties model
```

² [Releases · jyrkioraskari/IFCToLBD](https://github.com/jyrkioraskari/IFCToLBD)

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